

EXPERIMENTAL AND ANALYTICAL INVESTIGATION OF NATURAL FREQUENCIES IN CANTILEVER EULER-BERNOULLI BEAMS: EFFECTS OF BEAM DIMENSIONS AND SENSOR PARAMETERS

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ABSTRACT: The goal of this study is to experimentally determine the natural frequencies using modal analysis of the flexural vibrations of cantilever Euler-Bernoulli beams that have different sizes to verify the classical theory. We also investigate how the mass and position of the sensor affect the natural frequencies. For this, we extracted the first three natural frequencies through experimental dynamic tests, and we compared these results with those from the analytical study based on the classical theory of transverse vibrations. These tests were conducted on steel beams of varying lengths and widths. The sensor was placed in different locations on the beams. The comparison between the experimental values and the analytical calculations indicates that the accuracy of the analytical natural frequencies is influenced by both the length and width of the beams, as well as the mass and position of the sensor.

KEYWORDS: Beam transverse vibration; Euler-Bernoulli beam; Modal analysis; Natural frequency

1 INTRODUCTION

Modal analysis involves the study of dynamic properties under instantaneous excitations of structures in general and beams in particular. The latter are the most commonly used structural elements in engineering, and the transverse vibration of structures is generally the most worrying. The goal of modal analysis is to determine the natural mode shapes and the corresponding frequencies of the beam and the material studied [1,2]. These frequencies must be known to avoid them during dynamic excitations. Knowledge of natural frequencies can also be used to determine the Young's modulus of a material [3]. Many researchers have conducted experiments to extract these properties and understand some phenomena using bending dynamics [4-6]. One of the most important theories used is the transverse vibration theory, which is more difficult than torsional vibration theory and longitudinal vibration theory. There are many important applications of the transverse beam vibration theory; among them, we find the bending vibrations of beam structures, vibrations of shafts and rotors, etc.

2 ANALYTICAL STUDY

In the analytical study, we use the Euler-Bernoulli transverse vibrations theory to determine the following fourth-order differential equation of transverse motion in free vibration $v(x, t)$ [1]:

$$\frac{\partial^2 v(x, t)}{\partial t} = -C^2 \frac{\partial^4 v(x, t)}{\partial x^4} \quad (1)$$

where $C = \text{constant} = \sqrt{EI/\rho A}$, E - Young's modulus, I - quadratic moment of the cross section of the beam, ρ - material density and A - cross-sectional area.

Different configurations of steel cantilever beams were studied to determine the analytical natural frequencies to compare them with the experimental test results (beams without sensor mass, with a sensor mass and with different positions of the sensor mass), in addition to beams with different widths, thickness and lengths.

The following determined expression can give the i th natural frequency for a rectangular cross-section cantilever beam:

$$f_i = \frac{\lambda_i^2}{2\pi} \sqrt{\frac{E h^2}{12\rho l^4}} \quad (2)$$

where h and l are respectively the thickness and length of the beam; λ_i is the constant corresponding to the i th natural frequency, which depends on several parameters, such as the width b , boundary conditions, mass of the sensor and its position on the beam [1,7,8].

For analytical determination of constant λ with solution of equation (1), we consider three cases with cantilever beams boundary conditions.

1. In the case without sensor mass, we found the solution of the equation:

$$\cosh \lambda \times \cos \lambda = -1 \quad (3)$$

2. The case with sensor mass at the beam free end, λ is the solution of the equation:

$$1 + \frac{1}{\cosh \lambda \times \cos \lambda} - \frac{M}{m} \lambda (\tanh \lambda - \tan \lambda) = 0 \quad (4)$$

with M is the sensor mass and m is the beam mass.

3. For the case with sensor mass at different positions on the beam the final equation used for determining λ is:

$$\det \begin{bmatrix} P & Q & -N & G \\ R & P & D & -N \\ S & R & -T & D \\ W & Z & G & -T \end{bmatrix} = 0 \quad (5)$$

with:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} P = \cosh \lambda \mu - \cos \lambda \mu \\ Q = \sinh \lambda \mu - \sin \lambda \mu \\ S = \cosh \lambda \mu + \cos \lambda \mu \\ R = \sinh \lambda \mu + \sin \lambda \mu \\ T = \cosh \lambda (1 - \mu) - \cos \lambda (1 - \mu) \\ D = \sinh \lambda (1 - \mu) - \sin \lambda (1 - \mu) \\ N = \cosh \lambda (1 - \mu) + \cos \lambda (1 - \mu) \\ G = \sinh \lambda (1 - \mu) + \sin \lambda (1 - \mu) \\ W = Q + P\varphi \\ Z = S + Q\varphi \\ \varphi = \frac{M\lambda}{m} \\ \mu = \frac{a}{l} \end{array} \right. \quad (6)$$

A graphical method is used for the solutions of equations (3, 4 and 5) and the calculation of the determinant of the matrix (5) is done through Matlab.

The beam materials properties are given in Table 1. The λ calculated values are given in Table 2 for cases 1 and 2 and Table 3 for case 3.

Fig. 1. Cantilever beam with a sensor mass.

3 EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATION

Four series of dynamic tests were carried out using steel cantilever beams under free vibration (Fig.1). We used a special hammer for instantaneous excitations, and the measurements were performed with an accelerometer (Wilcoxon model 732, sensitivity 10 mV/g [$0.5 \text{ Hz} - 25000 \text{ Hz}$] fixed to the structure via a magnet). The natural frequencies were extracted using STUDIOVIB® software. In the first test series, beams of different lengths ($l = 50, 60, 70, 80, 90$ and 100 cm) and three different widths beams ($b = 15, 30$ and 60 mm) were used to determine the effect of length and width on the accuracy of the Euler-Bernoulli theory. The sensor is placed at the beam free end. According to the results of the first tests (Fig. 2), the length of the beam that gives results close to those calculated analytically is 1 m beam length (fairly long beam). This length is subsequently used for different widths ($b = 5, 10, 15, 20, 25, 30$ and 60 mm) because, in the analytical expression of the natural frequencies without sensor mass, the width has no influence. In these tests, the sensor was positioned at the free end of the beams.

In the third test series, the same 1 m beams lengths were used but with different thickness (Fig.4) and with 60 mm for width. In the last series of tests we have changed the sensor positions according to Fig.1 ($\mu = \frac{a}{l} = 0, 1/3, 2/3$ and 1). The beams thickness for the later tests is 6 mm , and the sensor mass is 24 g . The analytical calculation with different sensor positions allows us to trace the natural modes.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The Euler-Bernoulli transverse vibration theory can be used only for relatively long beams rather than for thicker beams (in our case, $l > 90 \text{ cm}$ with $h = 6 \text{ mm}$, $l/h > 150$) (Fig. 2). In this case the beam width has no effect in the theory without sensor mass (Fig. 2 and 3) and the analytical calculated frequencies are far from those measured for fairly short beams (68% error compared to 15 mm width and 37% compared to 60 mm width for $l = 50 \text{ cm}$ with 24% error compared to 15 mm width and 7% compared to 60 mm width for $l = 100 \text{ cm}$). Then we can introduce the width effect by introducing the sensor mass in the theory (Fig. 2 and 3). With the mass introduction, we find that the error has relatively decreased and the experimental results are approaching the calculated ones (46% error compared to 15 mm width and 13% compared to 60 mm width for $l = 50 \text{ cm}$ with 15% error

compared to 15 mm width and 5% compared to 60 mm width for $l = 100\text{ cm}$). The thickness of the beams does not have much influence on the theory and the variation of the frequency is relatively linear with it except perhaps with a thick beam. (Fig.4). The sensor position in the tests is very important to further reduce the errors. Because according to the results the position of the sensor at the modal nodes

gives analytical values relatively close to the measured values (Fig. 5-7) and the beam width has no effect in the analytical values.

Table 1. Materials characteristics of the beams steel.

Young modulus	Density	Poisson coefficient
200 GPa	7800 kg/m ³	0.3

Table 2. The λ calculated values for the first three frequencies in cases 1 and 2.

Beam width [mm]	15	30	60	15	30	60	15	30	60
Beam length with mass [cm]	λ_1			λ_2			λ_3		
50	1.7485	1.8066	1.8393	4.4392	4.5420	4.5420	7.4960	7.6251	7.7218
60	1.7623	1.8226	1.8393	4.4616	4.5743	4.6100	7.5225	7.6698	7.7218
70	1.7764	1.8226	1.8568	4.4860	4.5743	4.6497	7.5524	7.6698	7.7827
80	1.7912	1.8393	1.8568	4.5127	4.6100	4.6497	7.5683	7.7218	7.7827
90	1.8066	1.8393	1.8568	4.5420	4.6100	4.6497	7.6251	7.7218	7.7827
100	1.8149	1.8442	1.8597	4.5600	4.6208	4.6556	7.6504	7.7383	7.7923
Without mass	1.8751			4.6941			7.8547		

Table 3. The λ calculated values for the three first frequencies in case 3.

Beam width [mm]	15	30	60	15	30	60	15	30	60
Sensor position μ	λ_1			λ_2			λ_3		
1	1.8149	1.8442	1.8597	4.5600	4.6208	4.6556	7.6504	7.7383	7.7923
0.67	1.8558	1.8655	1.8712	4.6678	4.6809	4.6870	7.7522	7.8010	7.8271
0.33	1.8731	1.8750	1.8750	4.6409	4.6671	4.6801	7.7249	7.7867	7.8202
0	1.8751	1.8751	1.8751	4.6941	4.6941	4.6941	7.8547	7.8547	7.8547

Fig. 2. First frequency vs. beam free length.

Fig. 3. First frequency vs. beam width ($l=1$ m).

Fig. 4. First frequency vs. beam thickness ($l=1$ m).

Fig. 5. First frequency vs. sensor position ($l=1$ m).

Fig. 6. Second frequency vs. sensor position ($l=1$ m).

Fig 7. Third frequency vs. sensor position ($l=1$ m).

5 CONCLUSION

In this study, we aim to explore how beam dimensions affect the classical Euler-Bernoulli theory of transverse vibrations. The results we gather will help us improve the application of this widely used theory. Key findings from our research indicate that it is important to use a sufficiently long cantilever beam and to position the sensor at the modal node locations for any natural frequency, or near the fixed end.

Practically, using this method can help us determine the mechanical properties of a material, especially Young's modulus, by conducting a simple dynamic test on a cantilever beam and making slight adjustments to the classical theory. This adjustment will be the focus of our future research. The findings will also enable us to reduce the need for more costly tests on tensile machines to assess the mechanical characteristics of materials.

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